

1 **Netrin family gene products function to establish metastasis to distant sites in humans with**
2 **cancer.**

3 Shahan K. Mamoor, B.S., M.S., Ph.D cand.¹

4 ¹shahanmamoor@gmail.com

5 Chestnut Hill, MA USA 02467

6 East Islip, NY USA 11730

7 We measured total transcription using whole transcriptome technologies (RNA-sequencing) in circulating
8 tumor cells isolated from the peripheral blood of humans with breast cancer. Three members of the netrin
9 family, whose genes function in axon guidance, were among those whose expression was most highly
10 up-regulated (transcriptionally activated and differentially expressed at the transcriptome-level) when
11 compared to the transcriptome of normal (non-transformed) cells isolated from the peripheral blood: netrin
12 5 (*NTN5*), the netrin 1 receptor (*deleted in colorectal cancer* or *DCC*), and the netrin receptor D *UNC5D*.
13 Systems biological query using additional whole transcriptome technologies revealed gene products that
14 functioned in concert with NTN5, DCC and UNC5D, as well as gene signatures retrieved by netrin family
15 co-regulated gene products and biological processes predicted to be affected by their function using
16 advanced computational methods. The genes whose expression was co-regulated with these specific
17 netrin family genes at the transcriptome-level functioned in multiple neurotransmission signaling pathways.
18 Netrin family genes NTN5, DCC and UNC5D acted in concert with a zinc-finger transcription factor-like
19 GATA protein with developmental functions *ZGLP1*, an antisense transcript of a gene involved in
20 establishment of cell polarity, *PARD6* (*PARD6-AS1*), and *LINGO3*. DCC expression in primary tumors of
21 humans with breast cancer was significantly correlated with time to death in the context of metastasis to a
22 distant site, meaning increased DCC tumor expression predicted decreased patient distant
23 metastasis-free survival. Importantly, netrin 5, DCC and UNC5D co-regulated genes were found to be
24 decorated by tri-methylated lysine 27 SUZ12, EED and EZH2, components of the polycomb repressive
25 complex, PRC2 which functions to deposit the H3K27me3 mark. We reveal here functions of a
26 neurodevelopmental signaling system in metastasis to foreign sites in humans with cancer through whole
27 transcriptome study of a circulating tumor cell.
28

Results

We measured total transcription in circulating tumor cells (CTC) isolated from humans with stage IV breast cancer, from the peripheral blood, and used blood cells (whole blood) as a reference transcriptome rather than primary tumor to decipher how transcription was most different globally in the CTC.

Figure 1: Members of the netrin family are activated during metastasis in the periphery.

GeneID	p-value	lfcSE	stat	log2FoldChange	baseMean	Gene	Rank	%DE
126147	3.77E-09	0.782	-5.8940653	-4.609682	225.58	NTN5	507/	97.7
1630	5.69E-07	0.735	-5.0015499	-3.6768195	97.36	DCC	1434/	93.4
137970	5.34E-0	0.797	-4.0403988	-3.2222112	123.65	UNC5D	3503/21908	84.0

We discovered three members of the netrin family, NTN5, DCC and UNC5D as among the genes whose expression changed most significantly across the transcriptome in the circulating tumor cell in humans with stage IV breast cancer (Figure 1).

We studied transcriptional co-regulation across human tissues and multiple biological contexts to understand the relevant actors with which NTN5, DCC and UNC5D functioned. Co-regulation provides a strong level of evidence in actors a molecule is likely functioning in concert with. Zinc finger, GATA-like protein 1 (ZGLP1), leucine rich repeat and Ig domain containing 3 (LINGO3) and PARD6G antisense RNA 1 (non-protein coding) (PARD6G-AS1) were among the genes most closely co-regulated with NTN5, DCC and UNC5D (Figure 2).

Figure 2: Netrin family genes activated in circulating tumor cells are co-regulated with PARD6-AS1, LINGO3 and ZGLP1.

When querying netrin 5, itself, ZGLP1, LINGO3 and PARD6-AS1 were still co-regulated genes at the transcriptome level.

Query genes:

Rank	Gene	Entrez	Coexpression Score	p-value	%Co-reg
NTN5	126147	-3.2000	0.0031		

Coexpressed genes: out of 17894 total genes

Rank	Gene	Entrez	Coexpression Score	p-value	%Co-reg
1	ZGLP1	100125288	1.1547	0.0000	99.99
13	LINGO3	645191	0.9418	0.0205	99.9
395	PARD6G-AS1	100130522	0.6930	0.0000	97.8

We used systems biological tools to study the biological contexts within which netrin 5 co-regulated genes functioned to gain an insight into the range of biological functions NTN5 might participate in. Netrin 5 co-regulated genes functioned in neurotransmission processes (Reactome and GO Biologic Process systems analyses), indicating a higher-level physiologic function in which netrin 5 and its partners re-created during transformation and functioned in (Figure 3). Reactome analysis revealed “transmission across chemical synapses” “serotonin receptors”, and “Class A1 rhodopsin-like receptors”, while GO BP analyses revealed “transmission of nerve impulse” and “synaptic transmission” as relevant cellular processes.

Figure 3: Netrin 5, DCC and UNC5D likely function in neurotransmission-like processes.

We assessed a survival metric, distant-metastasis free survival in patients whose tumor expressed high and low levels of DCC (Figure 4).

Figure 4: DCC expression levels correlate with inferior distant metastasis-free survival (DMFS).

High DCC expression levels correlate with decreased time to death following metastasis to a distant site (distant metastasis-free survival, or DMFS).

High DCC expression: 72.18 months
Low DCC expression: 94.13 months

1 A netrin 5 gene signature was identified by co-regulation and a gene-set enrichment-like analysis
 2 (MSigDB; Broad Institute) was performed to identify salient features of the NTN5 co-regulated gene
 3 signature. We observed a strong enrichment of H3K27me3 targets among netrin 5 co-regulated genes
 4 (Figure 5).

5 **Figure 5:** Netrin 5, DCC and UNC5D co-regulated genes are H3K27me3 genomic targets.

6 **Gene Enrichment**

7 Step 1: Analyze top genes: Include query:

8 Step 2: Select a functional database:

9 **Results:**
 Tip: click on the numbers in the column T&A to see the enriched genes.

Term	p-value	q-value	T	A	T&A
BENPORATH ES WITH H3K27ME3	2.8E-11	4.71E-11	1094	722	101
SHEN SMARCA2 TARGETS DN	4.92E-10	2.73E-9	332	722	45
BENPORATH SUZ12 TARGETS	3.78E-5	6.88E-5	1013	722	78
BENPORATH PRC2 TARGETS	9.37E-4	2.72E-3	634	722	51
NIKOLSKY BREAST CANCER 16P13 AMPLICON	9.37E-4	3.74E-3	120	722	17
GINESTIER BREAST CANCER ZNF217 AMPLIFIED DN	2.35E-3	1.33E-2	325	722	30
BENPORATH EED TARGETS	1.2E-2	2.13E-2	1036	722	69
DODD NASOPHARYNGEAL CARCINOMA UP	1.53E-1	1.51E-1	1729	722	99
MOREAUX MULTIPLE MYELOMA BY TACI UP	1.53E-1	1.51E-1	367	722	29
NIKOLSKY BREAST CANCER 17Q21 Q25 AMPLICON	1.53E-1	1.51E-1	334	722	27
SENGUPTA EBNA1 ANTICORRELATED	1.53E-1	1.51E-1	157	722	16
NIKOLSKY BREAST CANCER 20Q12 Q13 AMPLICON	1.53E-1	2.09E-1	148	722	15
BANDRES RESPONSE TO CARMUSTIN MGMT 48HR DN	1.53E-1	2.21E-1	135	722	14

14 **Discussion**

15 We described here activation of netrin 5, DCC and UNC5D in the circulating tumor cell, isolated
 16 from the peripheral blood of humans with stage IV breast cancer.